

CaSDaR
Careers and Skills for
Data-driven Research

Careers and Skills for Data-driven Research
(CaSDaR)

A UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional
Skills Network+

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CaSDaR Townhall Launch
18th September 2025
The Library of Birmingham and Online

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Event Agenda

The event was held at The Library of Birmingham on the 18th September 2025, with hybrid attendance. Table 1 shows the number of people in attendance, both physical and virtual.

Tickets	Sign-Ups	Attendance
Physical	98	75
Virtual	189	90 (initially, then dropped to 60 after lunch)

Table 1: Number of people in attendance, both physical and virtual

Category	In-person	Remote
Academic/Research Leadership	7	5
Academic/Research roles	20	26
Data Management Specialists	20	58
Open Research	2	11
Policy and governance	2	1
Data Science and Analytics	6	14
Digital Research Infrastructure	3	1
PRISM	21	30

Table 2: Number of sign-ups, both physical and virtual, sorted by role. Abbreviations: PRISM = Professional Research and Investment Strategy Manager. NB. Some individuals did not provide their role when they signed up

Category	In-person	Remote
HEIs	57	125
GLAM	1	5
Government	16	20
Industry	7	12
Non-profit	8	8

Table 3: Number of sign-ups, both physical and virtual, sorted by employer type. Abbreviations: HEIs = Higher Education Institutions; GLAM = Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums. NB. Some individuals did not provide their employer details when they signed up

We decided to hold the launch event for CaSDaR at the facilities shared between the Birmingham Rep and the Library of Birmingham because we wanted

to honour the tradition of knowledge gathering and curation for the betterment of society.

The Library of Birmingham is located in Birmingham City Centre, on Centenary Square. The Library was renovated and re-opened in 2013 and is the largest public library in the UK, the largest public cultural space in Europe, and the largest regional library in Europe.

Photos from the event and the event agenda are below.

Figure 1: A photo of all in-person event attendees

Figure 2: An illustration by Jim Rogers of the CaSDaR Townhall launch event. Image available under CC BY-NC-ND [here](#)

Time	Title	Contributor/s	Location
09.30-10.00	Registration and Coffee	-	Mezzanine
10.00-10.30	Introducing CaSDaR	Samantha Pearman-Kanza	Studio
10.30-11.30	Data Steward Stories	Evangeline Gowie Angharad Green Robert Darby Anneke Lubben	Studio
11.30-11.45	Coffee Break	-	Mezzanine
11.45-12.15	Project Partners	Robert Andrews (ELIXIR-UK) Jamie McQueen (UK Reproducibility Network) Kevin Ashley (Digital Curation Centre) Nicola Knight (Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure)	Studio
12.15-12.25	Introducing the Poster Presenters	-	Studio
12.25-13.15	Lunch, Networking, and Posters	-	Mezzanine
13.15-13.45	Community Discussion	Samantha Pearman-Kanza	Studio
13.45-15.10	Data Stewardship Initiatives	Jenny O'Neill (Sonrai) Emma Karoune (The Turing Way) James Wilson (ARC-UCL) Tristan Martin (The University of Manchester) Michael Bearpark (STEP-UP and SCALE-UP) Kevin Ashley (Other EU Initiatives)	Studio
15.10-15.25	Coffee and Networking	-	Mezzanine
15.25-15.50	Participant Lightning talks	Elizabeth Newbold (UKRI-STFC) Catherine Jones (UKRI-STFC) Richard Campbell (University of Sheffield) David Leaver (UKCEH) Phil Reed (The University of Manchester)	Studio
15.50-16.20	Funding Call Launch	Samantha Pearman-Kanza and Louise Saul	Studio
16.20-16.30	Plenary: Next Steps for CaSDaR	Samantha Pearman-Kanza	Studio

Table 4: The Agenda for the CaSDaR Townhall Launch on the 18th September 2025, The Library of Birmingham and Online

Executive Summary

As the volume of data continues to grow, so does the critical need for Data Stewards, the professionals who ensure data is shareable, reusable, and FAIR-compliant. Yet in the UK, the role of the Data Steward remains under-defined and often under-recognised.

The Careers and Skills for Data-driven Research (CaSDaR) project aims to address this gap by helping to define the role of Data Stewards within the UK research landscape and advocating for their recognition and representation across institutions.

CaSDaR launched on the 18th September 2025 with a Townhall launch, hosted at The Library of Birmingham with hybrid attendance. The event presented the current landscape of Data Stewardship in the UK, introduced the mission and goals of CaSDaR, gathered input on what support and recognition was needed, and launched a funding call to support Data Stewardship initiatives.

The programme included sessions on the following:

- Inspiring Data Steward stories;
- Contributions from partners including PSDI, UKRN, ELIXIR-UK, and DCC;
- Lightning talks from UK and international Data Stewards (all participants had the option to submit lightning talks/posters);
- Interactive discussions with current stewardship initiatives; and
- Details of the CaSDaR funding call.

CaSDaR aims to bring together key groups across sectors to collaborate and support each other in creating a defined role and pathway for data stewards in the UK. Therefore, the launch presented an excellent opportunity to engage with the community.

The aims of this event were to introduce CaSDaR's team, to raise awareness of our remit, connect with the community, develop links with existing networks of Data Stewards, and to identify areas in which our community wants further action.

Keywords: Data Stewardship, Community, Launch, Development

Session 1: Introducing CaSDaR

2.1 Summary

This session was chaired by [Samantha Pearman-Kanza](#)

The aims of this session were:

- Introduce the high-level aims of CaSDaR¹;
- Provide a context for CaSDaR's aims in the UK research data landscape;
- Give a brief description of the objectives and deliverables of CaSDaR;
- Describe the [Values and Philosophy](#) of CaSDaR, including commitments to Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI); and
- Introduce the CaSDaR team.

This session provided a high-level overview of the proposed work of CaSDaR, how it links in to the UK landscape, and the structure of the team within CaSDaR as a 4-year funded project awarded by the UKRI dRTP call.

This session described the plans for a network of Data Stewards, including identification of community needs, generating clear definitions of the roles and career for people wanting to move into the role, promoting the importance of the close relationships between researchers and Data Stewards, and building a sustainable community for Data Stewards.

The key deliverables of the CaSDaR project were also described:

- Creation of a framework of roles, responsibilities, competencies, and career progression for people working in the Data Steward sphere;
- Curating a set of resources, such as job descriptions, career resources, and best practices;
- Reporting on UK Data Steward's skills gap;

¹A link to the presentation used on the day can be found here:

- Impact analysis of the CaSDaR's work on the community and the role of Data Steward in the UK;
- Provision of funding to support Data Stewardship through providing an evidence base; and
- Create an association to champion the needs of Data Stewards.

Also described in this session were the plans to run events to serve the needs of our community, such as Data Stewardship conference series, Bi-annual community workshops, training workshops to support the community, and Hackathons and Datathons.

This session has an ongoing purpose for our community; it serves as an introductory point of reference for members of the community who want to find out more about CaSDaR.

The slides for the session are available [here](#).
A link to the video can be found [here](#).

Session 2: Data Steward Stories

3.1 Summary

The aims of this session were:

- To reflect the variety of skills required for the role and acknowledge that Data Stewards often come from several disciplinary backgrounds and professions;
- Acknowledge that people working in Data Stewardship roles may not officially have that title and do the work outside of their official roles; and
- Highlight CaSDaR's ongoing commitment to ensure that we capture the variety of entry points and roles/responsibilities in the Data Steward role.

This session was the introduction to a proposed seminar series that we hope to offer for the future. By showing the variety of individuals who are involved in Data Stewardship (often without having that official title), CaSDaR aims to raise awareness of the role and contribute to a community definition.

3.2 Presenters

Our presenters were:

- [Evangeline Gowie](#), Open Research Coordinator and Administrator at the University of Reading;
- [Angharad Green](#), Data Steward at University College London;
- [Robert Darby](#), Research Data Manager at the University of Reading; and
- [Anneke Lubben](#), Director of Research Infrastructure and Facilities at the University of Bath.

3.3 Session outcomes

The session speakers were from diverse disciplinary backgrounds and had become involved in Data Stewardship through different avenues.

Evangeline Gowie's presentation highlighted the need for professional Data Stewards to be funded to provide continued support and maintenance for resources to support data sharing. Evangeline's job title is not 'Data Steward', however she has dedicated a substantial portion of her working time in supporting researchers with qualitative data to make that data open. Evangeline's slides are available [here](#) and the recording of the talk is available [here](#).

Angharad Green described how Data Stewardship can be an attractive career choice for individuals with experience in research. Angharad not only detailed how her previous research career was essential in developing her skill set as a Data Steward, but also provided an argument that research Data Stewardship is an attractive career option for individuals who have a background in research. The slides from Angharad's talk called 'My journey to becoming a Research Data Steward' are available [here](#) and a recording of the talk can be found [here](#).

Robert Darby showed how important it is to recognise and reward those in our organisations who support research data throughout the life cycle, and who frequently go above and beyond their job remit. As a Research Data Librarian at an Higher Education Institution (HEI), Robert has extensive experience in supporting researchers with their research data. Furthermore, Robert's talk underlined how Librarians play an essential role in our understanding of Data Stewardship. The slides for Robert's talk titled 'On being a university research data service provider' can be found [here](#) and the recording of the talk can be found [here](#).

Our final speaker in the session, Anneke Lubben, gave a truly inspirational talk that showed what is possible when people who have roles and responsibilities in Data Stewardship are recognised for their expertise. Anneke outlined how her experiences in the Research Technical Professional space have led to her ability to champion the RTP role, which is closely aligned with Data Stewardship, in a local and national setting. The slides for Anneke's talk, entitled: 'From Mass Spectrometry to National Strategy: My Journey in Research Infrastructure' can be found [here](#) and the recording of Anneke's session can be found [here](#).

One of our speakers has the job title of 'Data Steward', showing that when this role is recognised then it leads to opportunities for career development. However, the diverse voices of our speakers highlighted how often the responsibilities of Data Stewardship can be divided across multiple roles and there is potential for these activities to be unacknowledged and unseen within organisations, meaning that the importance of Data Stewardship in the day-to-day functioning of organisations can be mis-understood.

3.4 Session evaluation

We received significant informal feedback that this session was one of the most well received of the day.

In formal feedback forms, the Data Stewardship stories session was ranked as the second most popular session of the day, and from informal feedback was a highly requested session to run at future events.

We perceive that we met the original aims of this session, however we need to be mindful of representing disciplinary and organisational diversity in Data Steward stories moving forward.

In response to this feedback from our community, we intend to make a regular slot of Data Steward Stories, with community members describing their careers and activities in these areas, with the intention that the organisation of this will move into co-development with the community.

We intend that the Data Stewards stories sessions will move forward with the amended aims:

- To reflect the variety of skills required in roles involving Data Stewardship;
- Acknowledge that people working in Data Stewardship roles may not officially have that title and do the work outside of their official roles;
- Support sharing of resources describing the career trajectories for people intending to move into roles involving Data Stewardship; and
- Developing a space for the community to share their experiences in building these skills.

The audience for these will be individuals who are working in roles involving data management planning, management of research or data processes within organisations, or researchers who have an interest in moving into the role of Data Steward.

Session 3: Project Partners Panel discussion

4.1 Summary

The event was structured as a conference panel discussion chaired by our Principal Investigator, Samantha Pearman-Kanza, with representatives from CaSDaR's Project Partner organisations being given the opportunity to talk about their proposed involvement with CaSDaR.

The aims of this session were:

- Introduce our project partners, who represent stakeholders across the UK landscape and have the relevant experience to guide CaSDaR's activities and support our work;
- Give our project partners an opportunity to describe how they will provide strategic advice and oversight to the work of CaSDaR;
- To show how CaSDaR plans to work with our project partners and allow them to state why supporting CaSDaR was important to their organisations; and
- Ask our Project Partners to address the following questions:
 - Why is Data Stewardship relevant to their organisation;
 - What work is your organisation currently doing in the area of Data Stewardship;
 - Why supporting CaSDaR is important for their organisation;
 - Moving forward, what direction would you like CaSDaR to take; and
 - What do you envision a Data Stewardship community in the UK to look like, and how can CaSDaR support this?

This session gave an opportunity for us to shine a light on the organisations and projects that supported the CaSDaR executive team in their application. CaSDaR aims to work across disciplines and sectors, so ensuring that we have a wide base of communities that hold us accountable is vital to the sustained success

of the project.

If you are part of a community that you think may be interested in becoming a project partner for CaSDaR, then please email casdar@soton.ac.uk so that we can discuss this further.

4.2 Presenters

Our speakers were:

- Representing [ELIXIR-UK](#) was [Robert Andrews](#), the Lead Informatician at the Systems Immunity Research Institute, University of Cardiff
- Representing the [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#) was [Kevin Ashley](#), Director of the DCC
- Representing the [UK Reproducibility Network](#) was [Jamie McQueen](#), Data Manager at The Institute for Regeneration and Repair, University of Edinburgh
- For the [Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\)](#) was [Nicola Knight](#), Principal Enterprise Fellow at the University of Southampton

4.3 Session outcomes

Our project panel are represented on our [Management Board](#) board and their input is essential in steering the activities of CaSDaR.

The session not only provided an overview of the communities with which CaSDaR plans to work more closely moving forward, but also shows the essential role that CaSDaR can play in promoting Data Stewardship within different communities.

4.4 Session evaluation

Whilst this session was well received by our community, with over 50% of our community saying that they would like to see more of all of the sessions from the Townhall event, it was important for us to showcase how working with established networks is an important part of CaSDaR's activities moving forward. CaSDaR is keen to develop the network of project partners that steer our activities, therefore it is likely that we will run project partner sessions at future conferences, however we don't plan for them to form a large component of future CaSDaR events.

The aims of this event was to provide the background of the communities steering CaSDaR's activities, why Data Stewardship is relevant to them, and provide an opportunity for these groups to be recognised for their support for CaSDaR; this session met those aims however in the future it needs to be considered how these interactions will be framed for our community.

Session 4: Community Discussion and Consultation

5.1 Summary

One of the objectives of the launch was to understand the community and identify areas where the community would like action/input from CaSDaR. Therefore, we took this opportunity to use an anonymous feedback tool to ask the virtual and physical attendees for their opinions and needs in specific areas.

We asked the attendees a broad set of questions in the following areas:

- Their opinions about the role/career;
- Opinions on opportunities for career progression;
- What events these community representatives are interested in; and
- The preferred communication platform.

5.2 Presenters

[Samantha Pearman-Kanza](#) and [Louise Saul](#) supported this session on behalf of the CaSDaR team.

5.3 Session outcomes

We asked questions on the following:

5.3.1 Attendee Demographics

In order to understand the demographic that CaSDaR reached, we wanted to identify the job roles and types that were attending the conference. The attendees represented a wide variety of backgrounds and roles. The most common job titles of attendees were: Data Steward, professor, Data manager, and Data librarian. However, there were over 50 other job titles represented within our attendee cohort, which potentially shows the diversity of roles involving Data Stewardship skills.

We are aware that lots of individuals do data stewardship work as part of their jobs but are not formally recognised as data stewards, and CaSDaR wants to understand this demographic.

QUESTION: What is your job title?

Figure 5.1: Job titles of both physical and virtual attendees

5.3.2 Opportunities for career progression within the community

We wanted to understand the satisfaction that our community has with their current opportunities for career progression. The majority of the attendees did not feel that there were opportunities for progression within their current roles.

Whilst it is worth noting that this is reflective of our attendees and not necessarily of Data Stewards, it does show that there is an opportunity for further investigation into this and align it with other initiatives working to promote career opportunities for other research professionals.

5.3.3 Preference for naming of the Data Stewardship role

The definitions of the role of Data Stewardship are diverse so we asked our community how they would like to refer to the roles and responsibilities in this area, specifically whether they feel the term 'Data Steward' is sufficient.

5.3.5 Identification of events for the community

One of CaSDaR’s remits is to run events in the future for the community, so we wanted to understand which events would be required.

We ran an initial activity, asking our attendees to rank the following events in terms of relevance to them. The results are below:

QUESTION: Please can you tell us what sort of event you would be interested in by ranking the suggestions.

Figure 5.3: Ranked event requirements for attendees, with highest priority at the top

Where attendees stated ‘Other’, we asked them to elaborate:

Management; and Advocacy training.

5.4 Session evaluation

This session was essential for us to understand and record the needs and backgrounds of the diverse people who are engaging with our community which will support us in steering our future activities.

Given the aims of the session, the aims were met and we intend to build upon these questions in the future and iteratively create a picture that represents the interventions that are relevant to supporting the community.

Session 5: Other Data Steward initiatives

6.1 Summary

CaSDaR plans to work with existing initiatives that support Data Stewards and roles that are associated with Data Stewardship, as this will prevent duplication of effort and promote sustainability of CaSDaR's outputs.

Networks and groups, both in the UK and globally, have made significant progress to gain recognition for Research Enablers, Research Technical Professionals (RTPs), and Data Stewards. In order to ensure that we're representing Data Stewards across disciplines, maximising efficiency, and avoiding duplication of effort, CaSDaR would like to continue working with these groups.

6.2 Presenters

Our speakers were:

- Representing [Sonraí](#) was [Jenny O'Neill](#), who spoke about the way that Sonraí has worked to create and embed routes into Data Stewardship in the Irish research community;
- Speaking about the work that has been done to embed the skills associated with Data Stewardship by [The Turing Way](#) was [Emma Karoune](#);
- [James Wilson](#) presented how a community in [University College London](#) has developed a thriving group of professional Data Stewards;
- From the [University of Manchester](#), [Tristan Martin](#) spoke about how the Open Research Group in the library has made a convincing case for the professionalisation of Data Stewards in challenging economic times;
- The skills overlap between digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs) and Data Stewards was acknowledged in [Michael Bearpark's](#) talk about the work of [STEP-UP](#) and [SCALE-UP](#) in supporting the development of dRTPs; and

- Presenting the considerable work done by initiatives throughout Europe was [Kevin Ashley](#) from the [DCC](#).

6.3 Session outcomes

6.3.1 Jenny O’Neill from Sonraí

Sonraí (the Irish word for data) is the Irish Data Stewardship Network. Initially developed with support from the 2022 Open Research Fund call from Ireland’s National Open Research Forum (NORF), Sonraí has continued to evolve and develop. Our mission is to foster, enable and advocate for the development of research data stewardship and data stewards nationally. We have established network governance, developed our “Am I a data steward?” quiz, organised our first national conference and our first Masterclass. With support from the NORF 2025 Open Research Fund we are also developing a micro-credential in Data Stewardship, creating a model for how we develop discipline specific curricula and establishing a data champions program nationally.

The slides for Jenny’s talk ‘Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network’ is available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

6.3.2 Emma Karoune from The Turing Way

The interdisciplinary nature of the data science workforce extends beyond the traditional notion of a “data scientist” and we should therefore recognise and strive to professionalise all the ‘other’ roles that are part of the data science workforce. A successful data science team requires a wide range of technical expertise, domain knowledge and leadership capabilities. To strengthen such a team-based approach, we (myself and Malvika Sharan) recommend that institutions, funders and policymakers invest in developing and professionalising a more diverse set of roles, including digital research technical professional roles, such as data stewards, therefore fostering a resilient data science ecosystem for the future.

I will highlight work we have done in this area, including The Turing Way project – Professionalising traditional and infrastructure research roles in data science, in which we documented the different roles and competencies that make up data science teams at Turing and my current project, Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers, which seeks to understand the current landscape of skills, roles and team approaches in this area.

By recognising and professionalising these diverse specialist roles and how they collaborate within interdisciplinary teams, organisations can leverage deep expertise across multiple skill sets, enhancing responsible decision-making and fostering innovation at all levels. Ultimately, we seek to shift the perception of data science professionals from the conventional view of individual data scientists to a competency-based model of specialist roles within a team, each essential to the success of data science initiatives. See policy briefing note [here](#). The slides for Emma’s talk ‘Professionalising Data Stewards and all the ‘others’ are [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#)

6.3.3 James Wilson from UCL-ARC

A brief overview of how UCL is addressing the challenges of Research Data Stewardship from an institutional perspective, including our approach to professionalising the role, involving the community, and working on both research and services

The slides for James' talk 'Research Data Stewardship at UCL' are [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#)

6.3.4 Tristan Martin from the University of Manchester

Since the launch of the Office for Open Research at the University of Manchester in 2022 the Library has been undertaking a project on research data stewardship, in close partnership with Research IT and the University's Research Lifecycle Programme. It aims to develop and professionalise and enhance the data stewardship support and data steward community at Manchester, aiding researchers in the transition to a FAIR data research culture. This talk will explore the progress we have made so far, the ambitions we have for the future of the project, in addition to reflections on the challenges faced in making the case for data stewards and data stewardship in a higher education environment in which resources and budgets are under intense scrutiny.

The slides for Tristan's talk 'Making the Case in Challenging Times: The University of Manchester Data Stewardship Project' are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#)

6.3.5 Michael Bearpark from SCALE-UP

The shared purpose of STEP-UP and SCALE-UP is to build support and training networks for digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs), starting with the needs and experience of Research Software Engineering in defining itself over the past decade, and extending this to research data and digital research infrastructure / HPC roles.

STEP-UP is a regional project, an EPSRC Strategic Technical Platform focussed on London and surroundings. Its central aim is to help define and establish 'dRTP' and to support those who've chosen these roles. 'Data' was really the starting point for this work, as I'll explain, but 'research data engineer' and 'data steward' aren't the same, presenting challenges in developing training at different levels, and elsewhere.

SCALE-UP - no acronym - is a UKRI / NERC Network Plus, and is designed to share developments from STEP-UP and elsewhere nationally, primarily through managing a flexible fund for targeted dRTP initiatives across research software, data and digital infrastructures. Through scaling and supporting groups of research technical champions there's an opportunity to adapt training for specific research domains, while also raising awareness of the work of digital Research Technical Professionals and how important this is. There will be support available for hosting longer placements e.g. in central research computing teams for software / data / infrastructure, and mini compute clusters to support infrastructure training specifically and to make research computing more visible. The slides for Michael's talk 'STEP-UP & SCALE-UP: Building dRTP Support and Training Networks' is available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

6.3.6 Kevin Ashley from DCC

European initiatives to support data stewards are increasing their focus on professionalising the role and embedding it within the Open Research and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data landscape. The EOSC Association complements this by offering a roadmap with strategic recommendations to enhance data stewardship training, career paths, and institutional recognition. Organisations collaborate to mainstream Open Science practices, improve research data management, and ensure that data stewards are equipped with the necessary skills and institutional support. Projects such as Skills4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT have sought to provide resources to maintain research excellence. Ultimately, these coordinated efforts aim to elevate data stewardship as a recognised and essential profession within the European research ecosystem. The slides for Kevin's talk 'Data Stewardship Initiatives in Europe' are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

6.4 Session evaluation

Feedback on the session was good (Over 50% of attendees said that they wanted to see more of all sessions, and 4% said they would like to see more of specifically this session).

From an organisation perspective, the session enabled us to consider how we could go on to work with other initiatives to develop a 'Network-of-Networks' for Data Stewardship across the UK and Europe. This is likely to form a considerable part of CaSDaR's future work as it will prevent fracturing the landscape and promote collaborations to enrich the support delivered to the community.

Session 6: Lightning talks – results of Data Stewardship projects

7.1 Summary

This session gave an opportunity for speakers from a range of UK organisations to present their work on Data Stewardship. CaSDaR is keen to support groups and individuals who are doing this work, developing an evidence based approach for promoting professionalisation of the role.

7.2 Presenters

Our speakers were:

- [Elizabeth Newbold](#) from the [Science and Technology Facilities Council](#) presenting: 'Career Tracks for Data Stewards';
- [Catherine Jones](#) from the [Science and Technology Facilities Council](#) presenting: 'Data Sharing challenges for Energy Modellers: outcomes of a workshop';
- [Ric Campbell](#) from the [University of Sheffield](#) presenting: 'First Sheffield then the North: Creation of Research Data Stewards Networks';
- [David Leaver](#) from [UK-CEH](#) presenting: 'Data Stewardship in an Environmental Research Centre: the UKCEH model'; and
- [Phil Reed](#) from the [University of Manchester](#) presenting: 'DIRECT Framework: UK Community Development of a Research Technical Professionals Skills Framework'.

7.3 Session outcomes

Summarise the activities and outcomes of the sessions, include links to videos where relevant

7.3.1 Elizabeth Newbold: Career Tracks for Data Stewards

“What does a career track for data stewards look like?” If we want to consider career tracks for data stewards, we need to understand what the current situation is and the factors influencing career progression. The RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship IG conducted a survey and published a report “what does a career track for data stewards look like?” that explored the issues in an international context. The report (and accompanying data set) provides an evidence base for understanding how professional fulfilling data stewardship roles, but not necessarily formally identified as data stewards, perceive their career paths. The outputs of the survey led to the formation of the RDA Working Group Data Steward Career tracks which aims to develop a methodology for creating data steward personas and a sample set of personas linked to career tracks. This lightning talk will highlight some of the findings from the initial report and the status of the work from the recently formed working group.

The slides for Elizabeth’s talk are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

7.3.2 Catherine Jones: Data Sharing challenges for Energy Modellers: outcomes of a workshop

The Energy Data Centre (EDC) is a specialised repository and preservation service for the energy community and supports UK Energy Research Centre’s (UK-ERC) researchers to perform data management planning. The team includes both Data Stewards and Research Software Engineers. The EDC, in collaboration with the Data Infrastructure for National Infrastructure pilot project, ran a workshop in October 2024 focussed on the data sharing challenges for researchers who create and use energy models. This was a follow-on from a UK-ERC and the Centre for Research into Energy Demand Solutions workshop in 2023 on data sharing for Energy consortia which recommended further consideration for energy modelling. The workshop explored the different dimensions of energy models (scale, complexity, size of developer team, open or closed data), identified what were the main barriers to sharing both input and output data and suggested some recommendations to improve the landscape. Key messages included that working in multi-disciplinary field, such as energy, means that there is not just one community set of expectation or standards and that for some energy researchers using operational data from commercial companies is crucial. These and other important outcomes will be discussed in the lightning talk.

The slides for Catherine’s talk are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

7.3.3 Ric Campbell: First Sheffield then the North: Creation of Research Data Stewards Networks

The increasing need and awareness to make data and software FAIR in order to support the sharing and reuse of non-publication outputs, including the lack of concise and practical guidance on how to achieve this in the context of specific data types and disciplines has led to various approaches being tried and trialled. This presentation will detail the recent and ongoing work done at both

the University of Sheffield level and further afield across the N8 institutions. It will explore both success and failure (often a precursor to success), and ask if a network is a good start or a reasonable end point.

The slides for Ric’s talk are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

7.3.4 David Leaver: Data Stewardship in an Environmental Research Centre: the UKCEH model

The UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) ambition is to make the world a better place through science addressing climate change, promoting biodiversity and creating sustainable ecosystems. Effective data stewardship and management supports research integrity and transparency in tackling these challenges. The UKCEH Data Stewardship Team (DST) provides expert guidance on data management and stewardship, and the use of digital infrastructures. The DST consists of ten data stewards with discipline-specific expertise, distributed across four sites. A key focus of the team is support to researchers in data management planning using the Data Stewardship Wizard, augmented by targeted guidance through a Research Data Management (RDM) Portal. DST members also work on the curation of datasets for the Environmental Information Data Centre (EIDC), and many are practitioners in their own research field, which enables them to effectively support researchers at all stages of the data lifecycle, with an overarching aim to make research data and other digital objects increasingly Findable, Reusable, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The DST has developed a portfolio of RDM training courses, on topics such as FAIR data and the reproducible transformation of environmental data, which are offered to NERC PhD students and external organisations. Data stewards play a vital role in fostering a culture of FAIR data at UKCEH and across the wider environmental science community.

The slides from David’s talk are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

7.3.5 Phil Reed: DIRECT Framework: UK Community Development of a Research Technical Professionals Skills Framework

As digital research becomes more integrated into the arts and humanities sectors, the role of digital Research Professionals has become increasingly vital, facilitating collaboration and innovation. This term Digital Research Technical Professional (dRTP) is broader than Research Software Engineer (RSE) and data stewards, roles well-defined at many institutions in the UK. The growing demand for such roles has highlighted the need for clearer definitions of the skills and pathways for professional development. To address this gap, a new national ‘Digital Research Competencies Framework (DIRECT Framework)’ is proposed – a community-driven resource designed to define, visualise and track the progression of skills. The Toolkit offers a structured collection of skills, accompanied by visualisations. It provides value to individuals, allowing them to periodically assess their skills and identify opportunities for progression. Managers will benefit from a clear and transparent view of their team, aiding in task allocation. The Toolkit also covers non-technical skills, including management and interpersonal skills. This presentation briefly describes the latest Toolkit work, and

looks at how an open tool can be built and applied if there is appropriate initiative and commitment from the community. We will continue to collaboratively review the framework to enhance our collective understanding, ensure alignment with wider community goals, and identify any gaps, inconsistencies, or overlooked aspects of the framework that may need further consideration or improvement.

The slides from Phil's talk are available [here](#) and the recording is available [here](#).

7.4 Session evaluation

The aim of this session was to provide a platform for individuals conducting research in this space to present the results of their work and the aims were met. Feedback on the session was very positive and this session was the most well received in the formal feedback, with 23% of respondents expressing a specific interest in hearing more from individual projects, and over half expressing an interest in hearing more from all sessions, including lightning talks from data stewardship projects.

Moving forward, the CaSDaR team would like to develop these sessions in our events and provide the opportunity for individuals who are involved in Data stewardship projects to have a platform to present and gain recognition for their work to their peers. Often, Data Stewards are not incentivised to publish or share their work as a research output. Therefore providing a platform as a space to share work can create opportunities for development for individuals working in Data Stewardship.

Informing CaSDaR's future work

CaSDaR's Townhall provided an opportunity for us to engage with the community and ensure that we focus our efforts on areas that the community needs.

Based on feedback from the event, we plan to focus on these areas:

- Data Steward Stories as a regular remote event series, with the aim of increasing the evidence base of roles within Data Stewardship;
- Provide opportunities to promote the work by Data Stewards and individuals involved with Data Stewardship through regular events where they present their work;
- Create networking opportunities for Data Stewards to share their experiences; and
- Develop training to fill skills gaps identified through work with the community,

The Townhall event also allowed us to reflect on our strategy to engage with the wider community. The demographics of individuals who signed up to the event is on page 1; whilst we engaged effectively with individuals employed by Higher Education Institutions and Organisation who receive significant amounts of government funding, we did not manage to generate interest or reach individuals who work in Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums. Individuals working in these area have significant Data Stewardship responsibilities, therefore we need to ensure that we plan to engage with these communities moving forward.